

Thanks for participating!

Using this questionnaire, we would like to collect your impressions of 4diac IDE while performing the tasks.

Your answers will influence the development process of 4diac IDE.

Section A: Your work experience

First, we collect information on your domain experience.

A1. Name (required for assigning your questionnaire to your study results, answers are anonymized before evaluation)

Format: First name Last name

A2. Please describe your education!

School education if applicable, study programme and whether it was completed at a university or a university of applied sciences

Example: Grammar school with a major in languages, afterwards studied IT at a university

A3. Domain-specific experience in developing automation software (in years)

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A4. How many years have you been working for your current employer?

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A5. Have you used 4diac IDE earlier?

Yes

No

A6. If you have already used 4diac IDE: How often, how long, and for which purpose?

Example: used it for a few days within the past year during trainings

A7. Do you have experience with Eclipse IDE or other tools that are based on the Eclipse platform?

Yes

No

A8. If you have experience with Eclipse IDE or other Eclipse-based tools: How long and for which purpose did you use them?

For example: I used Eclipse IDE for Java developments in a course at university.

Section B: Questions on Usability

In the following questions we ask your opinion on the individual views of 4diac IDE. In this picture, we illustrate the meaning of the used terms:

B1. How easy was it to learn working with 4diac IDE?

	System Explorer	Application Editor	Properties View	Dialogues	Outline
very easy	☐				
easy	☐				
difficult	☐				
very difficult	☐				
not used	☐				

System Explorer

Application Editor

Dialogues

Outline

Properties View

B2. How efficient was it to use the tool (once learned, do you think you could productively use the tool in your daily work)?

very efficient

efficient

inefficient

very inefficient

B3. How many errors occurred?

Example: clicks didn't work in the GUI

	System Explorer	Application Editor	Properties View	Dialogues	Outline
no errors	☐				
some errors	☐				
many errors	☐				
too many errors	☐				
not used	☐				

B4. Were the editors pleasant to use?

	System Explorer	Application Editor	Properties View	Dialogues	Outline
very pleasant	☐				
pleasant	☐				
unpleasant	☐				
very unpleasant	☐				
not used	☐				

Section C: Questions on Utility

Finally, we ask you to provide your opinion on the utility of the tool. Your answers shall influence future development steps.

C1. What did you like about the tool in general?

e.g., useful features, tasks that were particularly easy to complete, design, ...

C2. What did you dislike about the tool in general? What are the things that should be improved?

e.g., unnecessary/complicated/missing features, tasks that were particularly difficult to complete, design, ...

C3. What are the opportunities for your company when using this tool in daily business?

C4. What are the risks for your company when using this tool in daily business?

Section D: Finally ...

D1. What else would you like to share with us?

Thanks for participating in our user study! We ask you to watch the video with our solution: youtu.be/xishphcgYmc